

**A PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY ON RISK FACTORS
ASSOCIATED WITH PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE AND ITS
MANAGEMENT AT A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL**

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DECLARATION

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It has not been submitted in part or full for any degree or diploma of this or any other University.

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In my capacity as supervisor of the candidate’s project work, I certify that the above statements are true to the best of my knowledge.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	FULL FORM
PUD	Peptic ulcer disease
HP	Helicobacter pylori
NSAIDs	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs
UGIE	upper gastrointestinal endoscopy
RUT	Rapid urease test
UBT	Urea breath test
H2RA	Histamine 2 receptor antagonist
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
IgA	Immunoglobulin A
ELISA	Enzyme-linked immune sorbent assay
PPI	Proton pump inhibitors
COX-2	cyclooxygenase-2
CCB	Calcium channel blocker
TCA	Tricyclic antidepressant
SSRI	Selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors
UPA	Ulcer protective agent
IPU	Idiopathic peptic ulcer
IPUD	Idiopathic peptic ulcer disease

ASA	acetylsalicylic acid (aspirin)
GC	Gastric cancer
GU	Gastric ulcer
DU	Duodenal ulcer
STG	Standard treatment guidelines
WHO	World Health Organisation
NEMLT	National essential medicine list for Tanzania
ACG	American college of gastroenterology
EHSG	European helicobacter study group
OCA	Omeprazole, clarithromycin, amoxicillin
OCM	Omeprazole, clarithromycin, metronidazole
OR	Odds ratio
CI	Class interval
CLD	Chronic liver disease
HTN	Hypertension
CAD	Coronary artery disease
GERD	Gastro oesophageal reflux disease
EGF	Epidermal growth factors
CBS	Colloidal bismuth sub-citrate

ABSTRACT**AIMS AND OBJECTIVES:**

To determine the prevalence of Peptic Ulcer Disease with investigation of various risk factors associated with peptic ulcer disease and to evaluate the usage of drugs in the management of peptic ulcer disease.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was carried out for duration of six months at the Gastroenterology department of Osmania General Hospital, Afzalgunj, Hyderabad. The data of 105 patients was collected by using data collection forms and was evaluated to see the prevalence of various risk factors associated with PUD and to assess the treatment.

RESULTS:

Out of 105 patients 57 were males and 48 were females. The age group 28-37 is more prone to develop PUD. Out patients (73%) were predominant than In patients (27%). Among risk factors *H.pylori*, NSAIDs, and stress were the most powerful risk factors for Peptic ulcer disease. Most prominent symptoms were epigastric pain which accounts for 66% followed by burning in epigastric region, acid reflux, nausea, vomiting, early satiety, bloating, fullness, loss of appetite, weight loss. Endoscopic findings shows gastric ulcers were predominant (70%) than duodenal ulcer (19%) and gastroduodenal (11%). Our findings showed that, the most widely used drug therapy is triple therapy which accounts for 30.4% and the most widely used PPI is pantoprazole (46.6%).

CONCLUSION:

The present study is focused on risk factors associated with peptic ulcer disease and its management.. Various risk factors like *H.pylori*, NSAIDs and stress are majorly associated to cause PUD. Other factors like age above 60yrs ,smoking, alcohol intake , spicy food intake, betel nut and betel leaves chewer, tea and coffee has significant impact on PUD prevalence. Triple therapy is most effective treatment for *H.pylori* positive cases which includes use of PPIs, Amoxicillin and Clarithromycin. Monotherapy with PPI was instituted in NSAIDs induced Ulcers and *H.pylori* negative cases for 14 days. Out of 105 cases, 97(92 %) cases were cured.

Keywords: Peptic ulcer disease (PUD), NSAIDs, stress, *H.pylori*, risk factors, management.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Approximately 25 million Indians are suffering from peptic ulcer disease at some point in their life time. Duodenal ulcers are 5 to 10 times more common than gastric ulcers. The incidence for duodenal ulcer is 30 to 60 years. The male and female ratio is 3:1. The incidence of gastric ulcer is usually 50 and over. It affect male and female in the ratio of 2:1. Each year there are 500,000 to 850,000 new cases of peptic ulcer disease and more than 1 million ulcer related hospitalizations. It is a chronic disorder producing life threatening complications such as haemorrhage, perforation, pyloric obstruction and inter tubular disease.¹

H.pylori is a common bacterial disease whose manifestations predominantly effect the gastrointestinal tract. India is prototypically developing country as far as *H.pylori* infection is concerned more than 20 million Indians are estimated to suffer from peptic ulcer disease.

For more than a century peptic ulcer disease has been considered to be a major cause of morbidity and mortality. Despite substantial advances this disease remains an important clinical problem, largely because of the increasingly widespread use of NSAIDs and low dose aspirin.² We discuss the role of *H.pylori*, NSAIDs, and other factors in the causes of ulcer disease and therapeutic and preventive strategies.

From clinical experience and retrospective hospital based surveys, it has been suspected that peptic ulcer is widely prevalent in India, more common among the population of South India than North India and the clinical behaviour of peptic ulcer in India is different from that in the West. In Hyderabad the staple diet (85%) is rice, and 70% used tamarind and spices daily. These agents may lead to ulcers. Hence, a study of risk factors and management of PUD is required.³

Study represents various risk factors of peptic ulcer disease (PUD), their complication and their management. We aimed to create awareness among people about the risk factors, its avoidance, and minimization, as in all age groups, a fast paced lifestyle, high level of stress, irregular eating habits, insufficient intake of fibre and water and lack of daily exercise contributes to prevalence of PUD.

1.2 DEFINITION

Peptic ulcer disease is defined as disruption of the mucosal integrity of the stomach and/or duodenum thereby resulting in a defect occurring locally due to the presence of an active inflammation. An ulcer in the stomach is known as a gastric ulcer while that in the first part of the intestines is known as a duodenal ulcer.² Ulcers occurring within the stomach and/or duodenum are often chronic in nature. Peptic ulcer disease (PUD) is a common disease and results in various complications such as bleeding, perforation, and gastric outlet obstruction.¹

Studies have reported the point prevalence of active PUD at 3% with a lifetime prevalence of 9%. *H. pylori* infection and usage of Non-Steroidal Anti Inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) have been considered to be the most important causative factors in the development of PUD. *H. pylori* is an ubiquitous, gram negative organism, known to have infected more than half of the world's population.

Upper Gastro Intestinal (UGI) endoscopy is usually performed to obtain a definitive diagnosis of PUD which is followed up with biopsy that can be examined by histology, Rapid Urease Testing (RUT), brush cytology, or even culture to determine infection with *H. pylori*. The current gold standard to diagnose *H. Pylori* infection invasively is a combination of RUT and brush cytology.²

Helicobacter pylori infection and the use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the most well-known causal factors for PUD. Although the prevalence of PUD caused by *H. pylori* has been decreasing because of eradication therapy, the prevalence of PUD induced by NSAIDs or aspirin is increasing because of the worldwide increase in the aging population.

According to previous studies, PUD has a strong association with cigarette smoking, advanced age, alcohol use, obesity, and specific chronic diseases. However, the clinical significance and pathogenic factors associated with asymptomatic PUD remain unclear to date.³

1.3 EPIDEMIOLOGY:^{4, 5}

According to latest WHO data published in 2017, peptic ulcer disease deaths in India reach 57658 or 0.66% of total death. The age adjusted death rate is 5.79 per 100,000 of population India ranks no. 53 in world.⁴

Approximately 500,000 new cases are reported each year, interestingly, those at the highest risk of contracting peptic ulcer disease are those generations born around the middle of the 20th century. Ulcer disease has become a disease predominantly affecting the older population, with the peak incidence occurring between 55 and 65 years of age. In men, duodenal ulcers were more common than gastric ulcers; in women, the converse was found to be true. 35% of patients diagnosed with gastric ulcers will suffer serious complications. Although mortality rates from peptic ulcer disease are low, the high prevalence and the resulting pain, suffering, and expense are very costly.⁵

1.4 ETIOLOGY:⁶

- *H. pylori* infection
- Non steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs usage
- Critical illness (stress-related mucosal damage)
- Hypersecretion of gastric acid (e.g., Zollinger-Ellison's syndrome)
- Viral infections (e.g., cytomegalovirus)
- Vascular insufficiency (crack cocaine associated)
- Radiation
- Chemotherapy
- Rare genetic subtypes
- Idiopathic
- Blood group preferences

1.5 RISK FACTORS: ^{6,7}**Risk factors include:**

- *Helicobacter pylori* infection
- Age older than 60 years
- Previous peptic ulcer
- Previous ulcer-related upper GI complication
- Concomitant use of corticosteroid, anticoagulant, antiplatelet drug (clopidogrel), oral bisphosphonates, SSRI's
- High-dose NSAIDs.
- NSAID plus aspirin use
- Chronic illness (e.g., cardiovascular disease)
- Alcohol consumption
- Cigarette smoking

Literature reveals a strong positive correlation between cigarette smoking and the incidence of ulcer disease, mortality, complications, recurrences and delay in healing rates. Smokers are about two times more likely to develop ulcer disease than non-smokers. Cigarette smoking and *H. pylori* are co-factors for the formation of peptic ulcer disease. There is a strong association between *H. pylori* infection and cigarette smoking in patients with and without peptic ulcers. Cigarette smoking may increase susceptibility, diminish the Gastric mucosal defensive factors.

1.6 SIGN AND SYMPTOMS: ⁶

Common ulcer symptoms include:

- Abdominal pain is the most frequent symptom of PUD. The pain is often epigastric and described as burning but can present as vague discomfort, abdominal fullness, or cramping. A typical nocturnal pain may awaken patients from sleep, especially between 12 AM and 3 AM.
- Pain from DU often occurs 1 to 3 hours after meals and is usually relieved by food, whereas food may precipitate or accentuate ulcer pain in GU.
- Heartburn, belching, and bloating often accompany the pain. Nausea, vomiting, and anorexia are more common in GU than DU.

- The severity of symptoms varies from patient to patient and may be seasonal, occurring more frequently in the spring or fall.
- Pain does not always correlate with the presence of an ulcer. Asymptomatic patients may have an ulcer at endoscopy, and patients may have persistent symptoms even with endoscopically proven healed ulcers. Many patients (especially older adults) with NSAID-induced, ulcer-related complications have no prior abdominal symptoms.

1.7 PATHOPHYSIOLOGY:⁸

Figure no.1 Pathogenesis of peptic ulcer disease

The gastroduodenal mucosal integrity is determined by protective (defence) eg: Mucus, HCO_3 , PG and damaging (aggressive) factors eg: acid, pepsin and bile. When protective factors decreases and aggressive factors increases, mucosal damage will result leading to ulcer formation.

1. ACID PEPSIN SECRETION:

Gastric perietal cells secrete isotonic hydrochloric acid. Acid secretion is stimulated by gastrin, acetylcholine and histamine. Gastrin is secreted by endocrine cells in the gastric antrum and duodenum

2. MUCOSAL RESISTANCE:

Some endogenous mediators suppress acid secretion and protect the gastric mucosa. Prostaglandin E-2 is an important gastroprotective mediator. It inhibits secretion of acid, promotes secretion of protective mucus and causes vasodilation of submucosal blood vessels. The gastric and duodenal mucosa is protected against acid pepsin digestion by mucus layer into which bicarbonate is secreted. Agents such as salicylate, ethanol and bile impair the protective function of this layer. Acid diffuses from the lumen into the stomach wall at sites of damage where the protective layer of mucus is defective. The presence of strong acid in submucosa causes further damage and persistence of H⁺ ions in the interstitium initiated or perpetuates peptic ulceration. H⁺ ions are cleared from the submucosa by diffusion into blood vessels and are then buffered in circulating blood. Local vasodilation in stomach wall is thus an important part of protective mechanism against acid-pepsin damage

3. NSAIDS:

Aspirin and other NSAIDS inhibit the biosynthesis of prostaglandin E-2 as well as causing direct irritation and damage to gastric mucosa. NSAIDS related ulcers will usually heal if NSAID is withdrawn and a proton pump inhibitor is prescribed for 4 weeks. If the NSAID has to be restarted (preferably after healing) H₂ receptor antagonists or proton pump inhibitors or misoprostol should be co-prescribed. If *H.pylori* is prescribed it should be eradicated

4. *H. pylori*:

1. To avoid the acidic environment of the interior of the stomach (lumen) *H.pylori* uses its flagella to burrow into the mucus lining of the stomach to reach the epithelial cells underneath where it is less acidic.
2. It also neutralizes the acid in its environment by producing urease which breaks down the urea present in the stomach to CO₂ and NH₃. These react with the strong acids in the environment to produce a neutralized area around *H.pylori*.

Table no.1 Difference between gastric and duodenal ulcer⁷

ULCERS ASSOCIATED WITH <i>H.pylori</i>	ULCERS ASSOCIATED WITH NSAID's
More often in duodenum	More often in stomach
Often superficial	Often deep
Less severe GI bleeding	More severe GI bleeding
Usually pain with dyspepsia	Sometimes asymptomatic

1.8 DIAGNOSIS: ^{9,10}**DIAGNOSIS OF *H.pylori*****Non invasive techniques:****A. Urea breath test**

Urea breath tests are simple and non-invasive, and have been used to diagnose *H.pylori* infection. Because *H.pylori* produces large quantities of the enzyme urease, these breath tests have the potential to be quite useful. ¹³C- and ¹⁴C-urea breath tests offer excellent diagnostic yield. Patients ingest a solution containing ¹³C- or ¹⁴C-labeled urea and an exhaled breath is sampled for isotope-labelled CO₂ released by intragastric *H.pylori* urease activity. The test can be completed within 20 minutes and is highly sensitive and specific

Figure no.2 Urea breath test is used to detect presence of *H.pylori*.

B. Serological test

Serologic testing is an accepted method for detection of *H. pylori*. Mean levels of IgG and IgA ELISA tests (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) are significantly higher in *H.pylori*-positive than in *H.pylori*-negative patients. Sensitivity of this serum assay is generally in the range of 80–95% and specificity in the range of 75–95%

C. Stool antigen test

Stool antigen testing has emerged as an alternative non-invasive means of detecting the presence of *H.pylori*. These faecal assays have become a useful test, and recent studies have shown a sensitivity value of 94% with specificity between 86-92%. Furthermore, it may be used to easily document eradication of an *H.pylori* infection if performed at least four weeks after treatment.

Invasive tests

- A. Upper endoscopy
- B. Rapid urease test
- C. Culture
- D. Histology

Endoscopic biopsy is the best and most accurate diagnostic method for *H.pylori*. Histological examination with standard hematoxylin and eosin staining provides an excellent means of diagnosis

Figure no.3 Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) stained histological section of the stomach mucosa showing *H.pylori*

1.9 TREATMENT OF PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE: ^{6,8,11}**1.9.1 SYMPTOMATIC TREATMENT****ACID NEUTRALIZING/INHIBITORY DRUGS**

Antacids are basic substances which neutralize gastric acid and raise pH of gastric contents. The most commonly used agents are mixtures of aluminium hydroxide and magnesium hydroxide. Aluminium hydroxide can produce constipation and phosphate depletion; magnesium hydroxide may cause loose stools. Many of the commonly used antacids (e.g., Maalox, Mylanta) have a combination of both aluminium and magnesium hydroxide in order to avoid these side effects. The magnesium-containing preparation should not be used in chronic renal failure patients because of possible hypermagnesemia, and aluminium may cause chronic neurotoxicity in these patients. Calcium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate are potent antacids with varying levels of potential problems. The long-term use of calcium carbonate (converts to calcium chloride in the stomach) can lead to milk-alkali syndrome (hypercalcemia, hyperphosphatemia with possible renal calcinosis and progression to renal insufficiency). Sodium bicarbonate may induce systemic alkalosis.

H₂ Receptor Antagonists

Four of these agents are presently available (cimetidine, ranitidine, famotidine, and nizatidine), and their structures share homology with histamine. Although each has different potency, all will significantly inhibit basal and stimulated acid secretion to comparable levels when used at therapeutic doses. Cimetidine 800mg at bed time for treatment of active ulcers. Ranitidine 300mg, famotidine 40mg, and nizatidine 300mg are more potent than cimetidine. Each can be used once daily at bed time.

Proton Pump (H⁺ + K⁺ + ATPase) Inhibitors:

Omeprazole, esomeprazole, lansoprazole, rabeprazole, and pantoprazole are substituted benzimidazole derivatives that covalently bind and irreversibly inhibit H⁺ + K⁺ +ATPase. These agents potently inhibit all phases of gastric acid secretion. Onset of action is rapid, with a maximum acid inhibitory effect between 2 and 6 hours after administration and duration of inhibition lasting up to 72–96 hours. With repeated daily dosing, progressive acid

inhibitory effects are observed, with basal and secretagogue-stimulated acid production being inhibited by >95% after 1 week of therapy. The half-life of PPIs is ~18 hours; thus, it can take between 2 and 5 days for gastric acid secretion to return to normal levels once these drugs have been discontinued. Because the pumps need to be activated for these agents to be effective, their efficacy is maximized if they are administered before a meal. Standard dosing of omeprazole and lansoprazole is 20 and 30 mg per day. Caution should be taken when using warfarin, diazepam and phenytoin concomitantly with PPIs.

CYTOPROTECTIVE AGENTS

Sucralfate is a complex sucrose salt in which the hydroxyl groups have been substituted by aluminium hydroxide and sulfate. This compound is insoluble in water and becomes a viscous paste within the stomach and duodenum, binding primarily to sites of active ulceration. Sucralfate may act by several mechanisms: serving as a physicochemical barrier, promoting a trophic action by binding growth factors such as EGF, enhancing prostaglandin synthesis, stimulating mucus and bicarbonate secretion, and enhancing mucosal defense and repair. Toxicity from this drug is rare, with constipation being most common (2–3%). It should be avoided in patients with chronic renal insufficiency to prevent aluminium-induced neurotoxicity. Hypophosphatemia and gastric bezoar formation have also been reported rarely. Standard dosing of sucralfate is 1 g qid.

Bismuth-Containing Preparations

Sir William Osler considered bismuth-containing compounds the drug of choice for treating PUD. Colloidal bismuth sub citrate (CBS) and bismuth subsalicylate (BSS, Pepto-Bismol) are the most widely used preparations. The mechanism by which these agents induce ulcer healing is unclear. Adverse effects with short-term usage include black stools, constipation, and darkening of the tongue. Long-term usage with high doses, especially with the avidly absorbed CBS, may lead to neurotoxicity. These compounds are commonly used as one of the agents in an anti- *H. pylori* regimen.

Prostaglandin Analogues

In view of their central role in maintaining mucosal integrity and repair, stable prostaglandin analogues were developed for the treatment of PUD. The mechanism by which this rapidly absorbed drug provides its therapeutic effect is through enhancement of mucosal defense and repair. The most common toxicity noted with this drug is diarrhoea (10–30%

incidence). Other major toxicities include uterine bleeding and contractions; misoprostol is contraindicated in women who may be pregnant, and women of childbearing age must be made clearly aware of this potential drug toxicity. The standard therapeutic dose is 200 g qid.

Miscellaneous Drugs

A number of drugs including anticholinergic agents and tricyclic antidepressants were used for treating acid peptic disorders but in light of their toxicity and the development of potent antisecretory agents, these are rarely, if ever, used today.

1.9.2 ERADICATION THERAPY:

- Eradication of *H.pylori* is recommended for HP-infected patients with GU, DU, ulcer-related complications, and in some other situations.
- Treatment of an *H. pylori* ulcer should be initiated with a PPI-based three-drug eradication regimen; the regimen should be effective, well tolerated, easy to comply with, and cost-effective

First-line eradication therapy is a proton pump inhibitor (PPI)-based, three-drug regimen containing two antibiotics, usually **clarithromycin** and **amoxicillin**, reserving **metronidazole** for back-up therapy (e.g., clarithromycin–metronidazole in penicillin-allergic patients). The PPI should be taken 30 to 60 minutes before a meal along with the two antibiotics. Although an initial 7-day course provides minimally acceptable eradication rates, longer treatment periods (10 to 14 days) are associated with higher eradication rates and less antimicrobial resistance.

First-line treatment with quadruple therapy using a PPI (with **bismuth**, **metronidazole**, and **tetracycline**) achieves similar eradication rates as PPI based triple therapy and permits a shorter treatment duration (7 days). However, this regimen is often recommended as second-line treatment when a clarithromycin–amoxicillin regimen is used initially. All medications except the PPI should be taken with meals and at bedtime.

Table no.2 Oral Drug Regimens Used to Eradicate Helicobacter pylori Infection: ^{6,7}

Proton-Pump Inhibitor–Based Three-Drug Regimens			
PPI once or twice daily	Clarithromycin 500 mg BID	Amoxicillin 1 g BID or Metronidazole 500mg BID	
Bismuth-Based Four-Drug Regimens			
PPI or H ₂ RA once or twice daily	Bismuth subsalicylate 525 mg QID	Metronidazole 500mg QID	Tetracycline 500 mg QID
Sequential Therapy			
PPI once or twice daily on days 1-10	Amoxicillin 1 g BID on days 1-5	Metronidazole 500mg BID on days 6-10	Clarithromycin 500 mg BID on days 6-10
Secondary or Rescue Therapy for persistent infections			
PPI or H ₂ RA once or twice daily	Bismuth subsalicylate 525 mg QID	Metronidazole 500mg QID	Tetracycline 500 mg QID
PPI once or twice daily	Amoxicillin 1 g BID	Levofloxacin 250mg BD	

• If the initial treatment fails to eradicate HP, **second-line empiric treatment** should:

- (1) Use antibiotics that were not included in the initial regimen;
- (2) Include antibiotics that do not have resistance problems;
- (3) use a drug that has a topical effect (e.g., bismuth); and
- (4) Be extended to 14 days.

Thus, if a PPI–amoxicillin–clarithromycin regimen fails, therapy should be instituted with a PPI, bismuth subsalicylate, metronidazole, and tetracycline for 14 days.

• Treatment with a conventional antiulcer drug (e.g., PPI, histamine-2 receptor antagonist [H₂RA], or sucralfate alone is an alternative to HP eradication but is discouraged because of the

high rate of ulcer recurrence and ulcer-related complications. Dual therapy (e.g., H2RA plus sucralfate, H2RA plus PPI) is not recommended because it increases cost without enhancing efficacy.

- Maintenance therapy with a PPI or H2 RA is recommended for high-risk patients with ulcer complications, patients who fail HP eradication, and those with HP-negative ulcers.
- For treatment of NSAID-induced ulcers, nonselective NSAIDs should be discontinued (when possible) if an active ulcer is confirmed. Most uncomplicated NSAID-induced ulcers heal with standard regimens of an H2RA, PPI, or sucralfate if the NSAID is discontinued. If the NSAID must be continued, consideration should be given to reducing the NSAID dose or switching to acetaminophen, a nonacetylated salicylate, a partially selective COX-2 inhibitor, or a selective COX-2 inhibitor. PPIs are the drugs of choice when NSAIDs must be continued because potent acid suppression is required to accelerate ulcer healing. If HP is present, treatment should be initiated with an eradication regimen that contains a PPI. Patients at risk of developing serious ulcer-related complications while on NSAIDs should receive prophylactic co-therapy with misoprostol or a PPI.
- Patients with ulcers refractory to treatment should undergo upper endoscopy to confirm a non healing ulcer, exclude malignancy, and assess HP status. HP-positive patients should receive eradication therapy. In HP negative patients, higher PPI doses (e.g., omeprazole 40 mg/day) heal the majority of ulcers. Continuous PPI treatment is often necessary to maintain healing.

Figure.no.4 Management of peptic ulcer disease: ^{7,11}

1.9.3 MANAGEMENT:

General measures

- Cigarette smoking, aspirin and NSAIDs should be avoided.
- Alcohol in moderation is not harmful and no special dietary advice is required.
- Reduce psychological stress, physical stress
- Avoid fasting and maintain optimum gap between meals
- Probiotics, especially strains of lactic acid-producing bacteria such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, lactoferrin, and foodstuffs (e.g., cranberry juice, ginger, chilli, oregano, some milk proteins) have been used to supplement *H.pylori* eradication.

1.10 COMPLICATIONS:^{8,9}

1. INTERNAL BLEEDING:

Hemorrhage is the most common ulcer-related complication, occurring in ~15–25% of patients. Bleeding can occur as slow blood loss that leads to anaemia or as severe blood loss that may require hospitalization or a blood transfusion. Severe blood loss may cause black or bloody vomit or black or bloody stools. Parenterally and orally administered PPIs decrease ulcer rebleeding in patients who have undergone endoscopic therapy. Patients unresponsive or refractory to endoscopic intervention will require surgery

Figure no.5 Endoscopic view of an actively bleeding ulcer; B, cross-section of the stomach wall.

2. PERFORATION:

Occurs in ~2–3% of DU patients. Peptic ulcers can eat a hole through (perforate) the wall of stomach or small intestine, putting at risk of serious infection of abdominal cavity (peritonitis). Approximately 15% of patients die from ulcer perforation

3. PENETRATION:

Peptic ulcer can penetrate into adjacent organs, especially with a posterior DU, which can penetrate into the pancreas, colon, liver, or biliary tree.

Figure no.6 Perforation into abdominal cavity.

4. GASTRIC OUTLET OBSTRUCTION:

Occurs in ~2–3% of patients. Peptic ulcers can lead to swelling, inflammation or scarring that may block passage of food through the digestive tract. A blockage may make you become full easily, vomit and lose weight.

Figure.no.7 Gastric outlet obstruction and penetration

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TREATING AND MONITORING PATIENTS WITH *H. pylori* ASSOCIATED AND NSAID INDUCED ULCERS:

- Assess patient allergies
- Assess patient use of alcohol or alcohol-containing products with metronidazole and oral birth control medications with antibiotics and counsel appropriately.
- Inform the patient of change in stool colour when bismuth salicylate is included in an HP eradication regimen.
- Assess and monitor patients for potential drug interactions, and adverse effects.
- Monitor patients for salicylate toxicity.
- Provide education to patients who are receiving HP eradication therapy, including reason for use of antibiotic and antiulcer combinations. when and how to take medications, adverse effects, alarm symptoms (Dysphagia, Pain on swallowing, Unintentional weight loss, Gastro-intestinal bleeding or anaemia Persistent vomiting On NSAIDs or warfarin.

- when to contact their health care provider, and the importance of compliance to drug treatment

NSAID-INDUCED ULCER:

- Assess risk factors for NSAID-induced ulcers and ulcer-related complications, and when indicated recommend appropriate strategies for reducing ulcer risk.
- Assess and monitor patients for potential drug interactions and ADR's (esp.. misoprostol)

PATIENT COUNSELLING:

- Weight loss in obese patients.
- Avoid spicy foods, Avoid drugs e.g. TCA's CCB's Anticholinergics, NSAIDS.
- Avoid hot beverages
- Maintain optimum time interval between meals
- Reduce psychological stress
- Reduce physical stress
- Cut off irregular eating habits
- Educate the patient about the current principles of therapeutic management
- Patient should be warned about the specific side effects to be expected from the regimen and what to do if they experience any of these side effects.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:**1. Zhen, et al. (2017) ¹²**

According to this study colonisation with *H. pylori* is a major risk factor for peptic ulcer disease, as well as gastric malignancies such as gastric adenocarcinoma and lymphoma involving mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue. Successful eradication is essential for primary and secondary prevention of peptic ulcer disease and gastric malignancy. In the primary care setting, one can adopt a stepwise approach with the 'test-and-treat' strategy to manage *H. pylori*-associated dyspepsia in young patients without alarm symptoms. Empiric first-line therapies should be for two-week duration; options include clarithromycin-containing triple therapy alone or with the addition of bismuth, concomitant therapy and bismuth quadruple therapy.

2. Lee, et al. (2016) ¹³

The study was aimed to investigate the prevalence of symptomatic and asymptomatic PUD during screening endoscopy and to identify risk factors for the presence of symptoms of PUD.

Use of NSAIDs is a risk factor for symptomatic PUD, but not for asymptomatic PUD. Excessive alcohol consumption and active-stage ulcers in patients with PUD are related to the presence of gastroduodenal symptoms.

3. Malfertheiner, et al. (2016) ¹⁴

Important progress has been made in the management of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and in this fifth edition of the Maastricht Consensus Report, key aspects related to the clinical role of *H. pylori* were re-evaluated in 2015. In the Maastricht V/Florence Consensus Conference, 43 experts from 24 countries examined new data related to *H. pylori* in five subdivided workshops: (1) Indications/ Associations, (2) Diagnosis, (3) Treatment, (4) Prevention/Public Health, (5) *H. pylori* and the Gastric Micro biota. The results of the individual workshops were presented to a final consensus voting that included all participants. Recommendations are provided on the basis of the best available evidence and relevance to the management of *H. pylori* infection in the various clinical scenarios

4. Lin, et al. (2016)¹⁵

This study aims to evaluate the applicability of nonbismuth concomitant quadruple therapy for *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) eradication in Chinese regions. systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials was performed . The study found that The *H. pylori* eradication rate was higher for nonbismuth concomitant quadruple therapy than for triple therapy. Moreover, higher compliance was achieved with nonbismuth concomitant quadruple therapy than with sequential therapy. Thus, nonbismuth concomitant quadruple therapy should be the first-line treatment in Chinese regions.

5. Seyed Mirzaei, et al. (2015)¹⁶

The study aims to assess the prevalence of IPU in Kerman, the center of largest province in south-east Iran. Their findings were :-there were not significant differences between patients with IPU and patients with peptic ulcer associated with *H.pylori* or NSAIDs regarding the sex, age, cigarette smoking, and opioid abuse. The study showed that in contrast to other reports from western and some Asian countries, the prevalence of IPU is low in Kerman and *H.pylori* infection is still the major cause of PUD.

6. Chung, et al. (2015)¹⁷

It is a systemic approach and explains about IPU and its treatment .An increase in the proportion of idiopathic ulcers has been confirmed worldwide, and peptic ulcer, once considered to be an infectious disease after the discovery of *H. pylori*, has gradually reverted to the original “no acid, no ulcer” theory. Given that the prognosis of IPUD is poorer than that of PUD associated with *H. pylori* or NSAIDs, careful evaluation of *H. pylori* infection by multiple parallel tests, detailed review of medication history, and thorough exclusion of other possible causes are of paramount importance before making the diagnosis of IPUD

7. Nagaraja, et al. (2014)¹⁸

The central aim of this systematic review is to evaluate the evidence for *H. Pylori* therapy from a meta-analytical outlook.

Current facts propose that a PPI, levofloxacin, and amoxicillin for 10 days is superior to bismuth quadruple therapy for persistent *H.Pylori*infection. The current literature suggests that probiotics and Chinese herbal therapy might be beneficial in eradicating *H. pylori*.

8. Sostresc, et al. (2014)¹⁹

This is a review article. Previous reports clearly demonstrated that *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) infection, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAID) or low dose aspirin (ASA) use significantly and independently increased the risk for the development of peptic ulcer disease. Today, the presence of *H. pylori* infection associated with low dose ASA and/or NSAID use in the same patient is becoming more frequent and therefore the potential interaction between these factors and the consequences of it has important implications. Therefore it is mandatory to establish clear strategies for the management of these patients. Further clinical studies focused on the combined effect of *H. pylori* infection with low dose ASA/NSAID intake should be performed. In addition, economical cost-effectiveness studies of the different strategies (*H. pylori* “test and treat”, long term PPI use) should be carried out.

9. Perez, et al. (2014)²⁰

Medications associated with developing uncomplicated PUD included current use of acetylsalicylic acid (ASA), nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), paracetamol, selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors, antidepressants, antihypertensives or acid suppressants. A nested case–control analysis was performed to calculate the odds ratios for the association of potential risk factors with PUD. The results indicate that several risk factors for upper gastrointestinal bleeding are also predictors of uncomplicated PUD, and that some patients do not restart therapy with ASA or NSAIDs after a diagnosis of uncomplicated PUD.

10. Jayaram, et al. (2014)²

This study aims to provide insight into the prescription pattern of drugs used in PUD in India. The data was extracted from the medical records of all patients diagnosed with PUD from June 2011 to May 2012. A retrospective analysis was done to study the prescribing pattern of the drugs. The current guidelines strongly recommend eradication therapy for *H. pylori* in all patients with duodenal or gastric ulcers, which will result in cure for over 90% of these patients, so that treatment is cost-effective as well as clinically beneficial. The inclusion of proton pump inhibitors with appropriate antibiotics has proven to maintain high eradication rates. Shorter courses of therapy with fixed combinations of *H. pylori* kits can improve compliance and decrease treatment failures.

11. Rimbara, et al. (2014)²¹

Study aimed to collect regional data on the susceptibility of strains of *H. pylori* to available antimicrobials. In most regions of the world, four-drug treatment regimens, including a PPI plus three antimicrobials (clarithromycin, metronidazole/tinidazole and amoxicillin), or a PPI plus a bismuth plus tetracycline and metronidazole provide the best results. Standard triple therapy (a PPI, amoxicillin and clarithromycin) should now be avoided owing to increasing resistance to this treatment.

12. Chen, et al. (2013)²²

The aim of the study was to investigate the association between *babA2* gene and peptic ulcer disease (PUD) and gastric cancer (GC) in *Helicobacter pylori*-infected populations. They evaluated the relationship between *babA2* and clinical outcomes (PUD and GC) using a meta-analysis. The results showed that the *babA2* genotype was significantly associated with an increased risk of PUD and especially in the subgroup of duodenal ulcer. Moreover, a significant association between *babA2* gene and PUD and duodenal ulcer) was observed in western countries but not in Asian countries.

13. Mwinyi, et al. (2013)²³

The Standard Treatment Guidelines (STG) and the National Essential Medicine List for Tanzania (NEMLIT) was first published in 1991. The fourth edition includes new sections on symptoms and syndrome. The STGs have been updated and are consistent with current national guidelines for diagnosis and management of common diseases. The guidelines also reflect changes in the management of various diseases including asthma and hypertension following recommendations from WHO and experts from international medical associations and agencies. This set of tools is meant to be a guide for quick reference and its recommendations are valid for most presentations of the conditions covered.

14. Suzuki, et al. (2012)²⁴

The aim of the study was to investigate age, sex, histopathology and *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) status, as risk factors for gastroduodenal disease outcome in Brazilian dyspeptic patients. Sex and age showed no detectable effect on CG incidence. The histopathological results showed a significant contribution of ageing for both atrophy and intestinal metaplasia. Presence of *H. pylori* was significantly associated with decreasing age and with the incidence of DU.

15. Antelo, et al.(2012)²⁵

The study was aimed to analyze risk factors associated with uncomplicated PUD and medication use after diagnosis. When analyzed by intention to treat, after 4 weeks of finishing the treatment, *Helicobacter pylori* was eradicated in 92.3% of patients in OCA(omeprazole clarithromycin,amoxicillin) 1,89.7% in OCA 2, and 82.8% in OCM. There was no significant difference between the three groups, regarding the eradication efficacy. Side effects were observed more frequently in OCA 2 and OCM groups. Primary resistance to amoxicillin and clarithromycin was not demonstrated, while 20% of cultured strains were resistant to metronidazole. In patients with peptic ulcer disease or non-ulcer dysplasia, triple therapy with omeprazole and two antibiotics is highly effective in the eradication of *H. pylori*. One week of OCA therapy is as effective as two weeks of OCA or one week of OCM, with less side effects.

16. Wang, et al. (2011)²⁶

The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence and risk factors of asymptomatic peptic ulcer disease (PUD) in a general Taiwanese population: The prevalence of gastric ulcer, duodenal ulcer and both gastric and duodenal ulcers were 4.7%, 3.9%, and 0.9%, respectively. Multivariate analysis revealed that prior history of PUD, high body mass index and current smoker were independent predictors of asymptomatic PUD. In contrast, high education level was a negative predictor of PUD (years of education 10-12: OR, 0.5, 95% CI: 0.3-0.8; years of education > 12: OR, 0.6, 95% CI: 0.3-0.9).

17. Lee, et al. (2010)²⁷

To assess the risk factors and the efficacy of medications of patients with gastric and duodenal ulcers among Chinese patients in Taiwan. Patients with gastric ulcers were younger than those with duodenal ulcers. Patients with duodenal ulcers had a higher rate of *H. pylori* infection, and those with gastric ulcers owned a significantly higher amount of aspirin and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug. Patients with gastric ulcers had lower *H. pylori* infection but more aspirin or NSAID use.

18. Salih, et al. (2007)²⁸

To identify and evaluate the relative impact of *H pylori* infection and other risk factors on the occurrence of gastric ulcer (GU), duodenal ulcer (DU) and gastritis in Turkish patients. Results showed that the presence of *H pylori*, aspirin, alcohol and NSAIDs intake act as an independent risk factors that had an augmenting impact on the occurrence of GU and only together on the occurrence of DU in Turkish patients.

19. Malfertheiner, et al. (2006)²⁹

The aim of the study was to update the guidelines at the European Helicobacter Study Group (EHSg) Third Maastricht Consensus Conference, with emphasis on the potential of *H.pylori* eradication for the prevention of gastric cancer. *H. pylori* eradication is less effective than (PPI) treatment in preventing ulcer recurrence in long term NSAID users. In primary care a test and treat strategy using a non-invasive test is recommended in adult patients with persistent dyspepsia under the age of 45. The urea breath test, stool antigen tests, and

serological kits with a high accuracy are non-invasive tests which should be used for the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection. Triple therapy using a PPI with clarithromycin and amoxicillin or metronidazole given twice daily remains the recommended first choice treatment. Bismuth-containing quadruple therapy, if available, is also a first choice treatment option. Rescue treatment should be based on antimicrobial susceptibility.

20. Gisbert, et al. (2003)³⁰

To study the concordance between ¹³C-urea breath test and histology in the diagnosis of *Helicobacter pylori* infection, and to evaluate whether there is a correlation between breath test values and histologic lesions of the gastric mucosa. A high concordance was observed between the ¹³C-urea breath test and histology in the diagnosis of *H. pylori* infection. A correlation exists between breath test values and histologic lesions of the gastric mucosa.

3. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES**3.1 AIMS:**

To determine the prevalence of Peptic Ulcer Disease with investigation of various risk factors associated with peptic ulcer disease and to evaluate the usage of drugs in the management of peptic ulcer disease.

3.2 OBJECTIVES:

1. To collect data from Peptic Ulcer Disease cases in a pre-designed forms for assessing different types of Peptic Ulcer Disease.
2. To assess the prevalence of various risk factors precipitating Peptic Ulcer Disease and their strength of association with Peptic Ulcer Disease.
3. To observe the management of Peptic Ulcer Disease.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 STUDY DESIGN: A prospective observational study.

4.2 STUDY LOCATION: Department of Gastroenterology, Osmania General Hospital, Hyderabad.

4.3 STUDY POPULATION: all patients attending Gastroenterology Department, diagnosed with peptic ulcer disease.

4.4 STUDY DURATION: 6 months

4.5 SAMPLE SIZE: 105.

4.6 STUDY CRITERIA:

Inclusion criteria

- Patients of age > 18 years
- Patients of either sex
- In patients and out patients diagnosed of PUD and on treatment
- Both complicated and uncomplicated cases

Exclusion criteria

- Refusal to be a part of the study
- Pregnant and lactating mothers
- Those with other gastric complications other than PUD

4.7 PLAN OF WORK:

PROCEDURE FOR DATA COLLECTION –

Patients satisfying inclusion criteria were enrolled. Informed consent was obtained from the subjects after explaining the purpose of the study.

Approval has been taken from Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC). Data is noted in a pre-designed data collection form and analyzed.

Data collection form includes patients demographic data, other details of patient, addictions, complaints, investigations and past, recent and current medications.

Data is collected in the designed form, from case notes, patient and attender. Data is analyzed for prevalence of risk factors associated with peptic ulcer disease and evaluation of treatment.

4.8 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS –.

- Standard descriptive statistics were applied to the data collected. The summary of categorical data was presented in terms of counts (n) and percentages (%).
- Odds ratio, confidence interval and level of significance were used to measure the strength of association between the risk factors and occurrence of peptic ulcer disease.

5. RESULTS

5.1 GENDER DISTRIBUTION

Table no.3 Distribution of patients based on gender

GENDER	TOTAL(105)	PERCENTAGE(100%)
MALE	57	54.2 %
FEMALE	48	45.7%

Figure no.8 Distribution of patients based on gender

Out of 105 Patients, 57 patients were male which accounts for 54.2% and 48 patients were females which accounts for 45.7%, hence Peptic ulcer disease was found to be common in men.

5.2 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON AGE

Table no.4 Distribution of patients based on age

AGE GROUPS	NO. OF MALES	NO. OF FEMALES	TOTAL NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
18-27	07	08	15	13%
28-37	13	23	36	30%
38-47	13	11	24	25%
48-57	07	04	11	13%
58-67	08	05	13	13%
68-77	02	01	03	02%
>77	02	01	03	04%

Figure no.9 Distribution of patients based on age

Age groups that are effected more commonly are from 28-37 Years, which accounts for 30% followed by age 38-47 years which accounts for 25%. Age groups 18-27, 48-57, and 58-67 accounts for 13% each, 2% of patients are from 68-77 age group and 4% are from above 77 years.

5.3 DISTRIBUTION BASED ON IN-PATIENT AND OUT-PATIENT**Table no.5 Distribution of subjects based on in-patient and out-patient data**

Total	105	100%
Out Patients	77	73.3%
In-Patients	28	26.6%

Figure no. 10 Distribution of Subjects based on In-patient and Out-Patient Data

According to Distribution of Data based on In-patients and Out-patients, it was found that 73.3% were Out Patients and 26.6% were In Patients which includes both Male and Female Patients.

5.4 PREVALENCE OF RISK FACTORS

Table no.6 Categorization based on dependent and independent risk factors

INDEPENDENT FACTORS				DEPENDENT FACTORS			
PARAMETER	NO.OF PATIENTS			PARAMETER	NO.OF PATIENTS		
	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL		MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
<i>H.Pylori</i>	18	14	32	TEA	32	13	21
NSAIDS	09	18	27	SPICY FOOD	27	23	49
STRESS	18	27	45	BETLE NUT	45	03	13
AGE> 60YRS	10	07	17	BETEL LEAF	17	3	04
SMOKING	21	00	21				
ALCOHOL	21	00	21				

Figure no. 11 Categorization based on dependent and independent risk factors

Independent factors: Those which can solely cause Peptic ulcer disease

Dependent factors: Those which cannot cause Peptic ulcer disease alone

Among independent factors *H.pylori*, NSAIDS and stress were more prevalent and among dependent factors tea intake and spicy food were more prevalent.

5.5 PROMINENT SYMPTOMS

Table no.7 Prominent symptoms observed

SYMPTOM	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE(%)
Epigastric pain	69	66.6
Burning in epigastric region	4	3.8
water brash	3	2.8
Nausea, Vomiting	12	11.4
Early satiety	3	2.8
Bloating	5	4.7
Fullness	4	3.8
Loss of appetite	02	1.9
Weight loss	02	1.9

Figure no.12 Prominent symptoms observed

Epigastric pain was most common symptom which accounts for 67%, followed by nausea and vomiting, burning in epigastric region, bloating, fullness, Acid reflux, weight loss.

5.6 LOCATION AND NUMBER OF ULCERS:**Table no.8 Distribution based on location and number of ulcers.**

LOCATION	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
GASTRIC	74	70.4%
SINGLE	47	63.5%
MULTIPLE	14	18.9%
DUODENAL	19	18.09%
SINGLE	11	57.8%
MULTIPLE	08	42.2%
BOTH	12	11.4%
SINGLE	03	25%
MULTIPLE	09	75%

Figure no.13 Distribution based on location and number of ulcers.

Most common type of peptic ulcer disease observed was gastric ulcer which accounts for 70% of total peptic ulcer disease cases, followed by duodenal ulcer which accounts for 19% and gastroduodenal ulcer 11%.

5.7 CO-MORBIDITIES OBSERVED

Table no.9 Distribution based on co-morbidities

S.No.	CO-MORBID CONDITION	NO. OF PATIENTS
1	LIVER IMPAIRMENT	15
2	HIATAL HERNIA	12
3	THYROID	9
4	PULMONARY DISEASES	7
5	DIABETES	6
6	HYPERTENSION	5
7	NEUROPATHIC PAIN	5
8	RENAL IMPAIRMENT	4
9	ANXIETY/DEPRESSION	4
10	GASTRO OESOPHAGEAL REFLUX DISEASE	4
11	MIGRAINE	3
12	ANAEMIA	2
13	CAD	2
14	SPONDYLITIS	1

Figure no.14 Distribution based on co-morbidities

Most common co-morbid condition was liver impairment and hiatal hernia followed by thyroid disorders, pulmonary diseases, diabetes, hypertension, neuropathic pain, renal impairment, anxiety.

5.8 RAPID UREASE TEST FINDINGS

Table no.10 Rapid urease test findings

RUT POSITIVE	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
GASTRIC ULCER	18	68
DUODENAL ULCER	09	18
GASTRODUODENAL ULCER	05	14

Figure no.15 Rapid Urease Test findings

Rapid Urease Test was performed to evaluate *H.pylori* infection. 32 cases were found to be positive. Out of which 68% were gastric ulcers, 18% were duodenal ulcers and 14% were gastroduodenal ulcers.

5.9 USAGE OF PROTON PUMP INHIBITORS**Table no.11 Distribution of types of proton pump inhibitors used**

TYPES OF PPI	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
PANTOPRAZOLE	49	46.6%
ESOMEPRAZOLE	33	31.4%
RABEPRAZOLE	19	18%
LANSOPRAZOLE	04	3.8%

■ PANTOPRAZOLE ■ ESOMEPRAZOLE
■ RABEPRAZOLE ■ LANSOPRAZOLE

Figure no.16 Distribution of types of proton pump inhibitors used

The most widely used PPI is Pantoprazole which accounts for 47%, followed by Esomeprazole 31%, Rabeprazole 18% and Lansoprazole 4%

5.10 DRUG THERAPY:**Table no.12 Drug therapy given to peptic ulcer disease patients**

THERAPY	GASTRIC ULCER	DUODENAL ULCER	BOTH	TOTAL	PERCENT AGE
MONOTHERAPY	24	02	01	27	25.7%
TRIPLE THERAPY	17	10	05	32	30.4%
PPI+ULCER PROTECTIVE AGENT(UPA)	09	02	04	15	14.2%
PPI+DOMPERIDONE	09	-	01	10	9.5%
PPI+ ANTACIDS	06	01	01	08	7.6%
PPI+DOMPERIDONE+UPA	05	-	-	05	4.7%
PPI+ANTICHOLINERGIC+DOMPERIDONE	01	01	-	02	1.9%
PPI+H2 RECEPTOR BLOCKER	01	01	-	02	1.9%
PPI+ANTIBIOTIC	01	01	-	02	1.9%
PPI+PROKINETIC	01	01	-	02	1.9%

Figure no.18 Drug therapy given to peptic ulcer disease patients

The most widely used drug therapy is triple therapy, which is prescribed in the form of Pantocid kit (Pantoprazole, Amoxicillin, Clarithromycin) or Nexpro kit (Esomeprazole, Amoxicillin, Clarithromycin) which accounts for 30.4% of cases.

The next most widely used drug therapy is Monotherapy (Pantoprazole, Esomeprazole, Lansoprazole, and Rabiprazole) accounts for 25.7 % of cases.

Other therapies, include PPI plus ulcer protective agents(suralfate), PPI plus domperidone, PPI plus antacids (aluminium hydroxide, magnesium carbonate), PPI plus domperidone plus UPA, PPI plus anticholinergic(metoclopramide) plus domperidone, PPI plus H2 receptor blocker(Ranitidine) , PPI plus antibiotic, PPI plus prokinetic

5.11 DIFFERENT TYPES OF *H.PYLORI* KIT PRESCRIBED

Table no.13 Types of *H.pylori* kit prescribed in eradication therapy

TYPE OF TRIPLE THERAPY	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
NO. OF PANTOCID KIT PRESCRIBED	14	43%
NO. OF NEXPRO KIT PRESCRIBED	18	57%

Figure no.18 Types of *H.pylori* kit prescribed in eradication therapy

A total of 32 *H.pylori* positive cases were detected, out of which 14 cases were given Pantocid kit, 18 cases were given Nexpro kit.

Pantocid kit comprises of Pantoprazole, Amoxicillin, Clarithromycin

Nexpro kit comprises of Esomeprazole, Amoxicillin, Clarithromycin

5.12 EFFICACY OF THE TREATMENT

Table no.14 Treatment efficacy

	NO. OF CASES	PERCENTAGE
CURED	97	92%
RECURRENT	08	8%

Figure no.19 Treatment efficacy

Patients were said to be cured when their symptoms resolved, and about 92% cases were cured. Patients in whom symptoms reappear even after taking therapy successfully, are listed under recurrent cases and about 8% of cases had recurrent symptoms.

5.13 COMPLICATIONS:**Table no.15 Complications of Peptic Ulcer Disease**

TYPE OF COMPLICATION	NO.OF .CASES (n=105)
PERFORATION	0
BLEEDING	10
GASTRIC OUTLET OBSTRUCTION	0

Figure no.20 Complications of Peptic Ulcer Disease

Out of 105 cases, only 10% of patients were found to exhibit upper gastro intestinal bleeding.

5.14 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS BASED ON AGE (TOTAL):

Figure no. 21 Stem and leaf plot of age of patients

Figure no.21 Box whisker plot showing distribution of age of patients (n=105)

From both of these plots it is clear that the ages of patients varied from 18-85. The Box plot which shows five number summary (lowest number, lower quartile, central quartile, upper quartile and highest number.) of the data (ages of the patients).

Apart from descriptive statistics, we have used odds ratio, confidence interval and significance level to measure the strength of association between risk factors and occurrence of peptic ulcer disease.

Table no. 16 Odds ratio for various risk factors

S.No	RISK FACTORS	ODDS RATIO	CONFIDENCE INTERVAL	SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL
1	NSAIDS	1.9167	1.1797-3.1141	0.0086
2	<i>H. PYLORI</i>	0.5217	0.3211-0.8477	0.0086
3	SPICY FOOD	0.8750	0.5473-1.3989	0.5770
4	STRESS	0.7797	0.4868-1.2486	0.3003
5	SMOKING	0.2500	0.1443-0.4331	<0.0001
6	ALCOHOLISM	0.2500	0.1443-0.4331	<0.0001
7	TEA OR COFFEE INTAKE	0.2500	0.1443-0.4331	<0.0001
8	AGE >60 YEARS	0.1932	0.1076-0.3469	<0.0001
9	TOBACCO CHEWER	0.1413	0.0745-0.2682	<0.0001
10	BETEL LEAVES	0.0396	0.0141-0.1115	<0.0001

Based upon odds ratio, *H. pylori*, NSAIDs, smoking, age, alcohol, tea or coffee intake, tobacco and betel leaves intake have significant strength of association with the occurrence of peptic ulcer disease at significance level of less than or equal to 5% (0.05). Other less significant factors were stress and spicy food.

6. DISCUSSION

We have performed a prospective observational study in Gastroenterology Department, to assess risk factors associated with PUD and its management.

In present study, a total of 105 patients were observed of which Male population was predominant with 57 cases (54%) than female population with 48 cases (46%), which were in accordance with Mirzaei, et al.(2015), Najm, et al.(2011).^{16,32} It was seen that people of age group 28-37 were more effected with disease (30%).This may be due to the reason that, people in this age develop habits like smoking, alcoholism, eating spicy and junk foods also due to work related stress. Out patients (77%) were predominant than In patients(28%).

In present study NSAIDs, *H.pylori* and stress were found to be the most powerful independent risk factors for PUD, which is in accordance with Perez et al (2014)²⁰ had similar findings. Other independent risk factors include, age (above 60yrs), smoking and alcohol. Dependent factors were tea or coffee intake, spicy food, betel nut and betel leaves, amongst which tea intake and spicy food were more powerful.

About 27 (26%) NSAIDs use cases were reported. Statistical analysis showed an odds ratio of 1.9167.NSAIDs use has a strong association with ulcer formation and hence the major risk factor in this population and these findings were similar with Salih, et al.(2007).²⁸*H.pylori* was the next independent risk factor (30%) followed by smoking (20%).

Alcoholism was reported in 20% of patients. Alcohol intake induces duodenal ulcers. Age >60 yrs is an independent risk factor contributing to 16% of patients.

Certain lifestyle factors such as consumption of tobacco, alcohol, tea, coffee, betel nut and spicy foods are believed to stimulate gastric acid secretion .Use of NSAID is a risk factor for gastric ulcer, excess alcohol consumption and active stage ulcer in patients with PUD are related to presence of gastroduodenal symptoms. PUD has a strong association with cigarette smoking, advanced age, alcohol use, obesity, and specific chronic diseases according to study conducted by Lee SP, et al. (2016).¹³

Most prominent symptoms were epigastric pain which accounts for 66% followed by burning in epigastric region, water brash, nausea, vomiting, early satiety, bloating, fullness, loss of appetite, weight loss. These findings were in accordance with Rai RR ,et al.(2017).¹

According to endoscopic findings Gastric ulcer was predominant (70%) than duodenal ulcer (19%) and gastroduodenal (11%). These findings were in accordance with Jayaram et al. (2014)², Gisbert et al (2003)³⁰, Sonnenberg, et al. (2010)³¹ and Feldman, et al. (2013)³³

Liver impairment was found as major comorbidity. Other comorbid conditions were hiatal hernia, pulmonary disease, thyroid, DM, HTN, neuropathic pain, renal disease, anxiety or depression, GERD, migraine, anaemia, CAD.

The diagnosis of PUD was made on basis of endoscopy and the definitive diagnosis for determination of *H.pylori* infection was based on RUT and biopsy. It was noted that these tests were done only in small percentage of patients and empirical treatment was started which is in consistent with Gisbert, et al. (2003).³⁰

RUT test was performed in 32 cases, and from those which were *H.pylori* positive, 18 cases (68%) were gastric ulcer, 9 (18%) were duodenal ulcer and 5 (14%) were both. For patients with risk factors for uncomplicated PUD, it is important to take preventive measures to reduce the likelihood of ulcer development. According to recommendations of Maastricht III Consensus Report (2007) the rapid urease test can detect the presence of *H. pylori*, within one hour with a satisfactory accuracy (>90%). False negative results can occur in patients taking antisecretory drugs.²⁹

GI symptoms in individuals receiving ASA or NSAID treatment may be more closely monitored than in non-users of these drugs, and this might increase the likelihood of ASA or NSAID users eventually being diagnosed with uncomplicated PUD compared with non-users (i.e. detection bias), this was in consistence with Perez, et al. (2014).²⁰

Maastricht III Consensus Report (2007) suggested that patients who are receiving long term aspirin and have an ulcer disease and a history of significant bleeding should be tested for *H. pylori* infection and, if positive, be given eradication therapy. Patients receiving long term PPI treatment for prevention of NSAID ulcers should be tested for *H. pylori* to reduce the PPI-*H. pylori* interaction leading to accelerated loss of specialised glands and atrophic gastritis.²⁹ In our study 10 cases of UGI bleeding were observed.

Therapy was chosen based on regional bacterial resistance patterns, local recommendation, and drug availability, which were in accordance with Fashner, et al. (2013).³⁴

In the present study we found that the most widely used PPI is Pantoprazole (46.6%) as compared to Esomeprazole (31%), Lansoprazole (4%), Rabeprazole (18%).

Our findings showed that, the most widely used drug therapy is triple therapy which accounts for 30.4% followed by monotherapy which is 25.7% and other therapies includes PPI +ulcer protective agents, PPI+domperidone, PPI+antacids, PPI+domperidone+UPA, PPI +anticholinergic+domperidone, PPI +H₂ receptor blocker, PPI +antibiotic, PPI +prokinetic

Monotherapy with PPI for 2 weeks was most common in patients with uncomplicated PUD and combination of antibiotics with PPI (triple therapy) was given to *H.pylori* positive cases. The most widely prescribed kit was NEXPRO kit (esomeprazole, amoxicillin, clarithromycin) as compared to PANTOCID kit (pantop, amoxicillin, clarithromycin) this was in contrast with Nagraj, et al. (2014). Eradication therapy was given for 2 weeks and after that maintenance therapy with PPIs was given for 4 weeks. Maastricht III Consensus Report(2007)²⁹ formulated that standard triple therapy composed of PPI, clarithromycin and amoxicillin/or metronidazole is more successful if extended to more than seven days. Increased resistance to antibiotics used in the PPI triple therapy needs to be considered in the selection of treatment. Recently sequential treatment consisting of five days of a PPI plus amoxicillin followed by five additional days of a PPI plus clarithromycin plus tinidazole has been shown to be better than the combination of a PPI plus amoxicillin and clarithromycin for seven days and deserves further evaluation in different regions. Bismuth based quadruple therapy is a preferred option as second choice treatment if not previously used. However the participants highlighted the fact that bismuth is not currently available in many countries.

It was observed in our study that 81% cases were cured and 19% were recurrent. Studies indicate that eradication of infection not only heals peptic ulcers, but also reduces the ulcer recurrence rate. Maintenance therapy should be continued with PPI use following *H. pylori* eradication in all patients to prevent ulcer recurrence or complications. According to Lee SW et al. (2010) Standard dose PPI treatment should be prescribed for 4 weeks in patients with duodenal ulcers and for 8 weeks in patients with gastric ulcers.²⁷

The strength of our study is occurrence of various dependent and independent factors in Indian population. The present study has some limitations. Firstly, RUT was not performed in all patients due to unavailability, insensitivity and unaffordability. Secondly, there is a possibility that some patients were unaware that they were taking NSAIDs or its consequences on the development of PUD.

7. CONCLUSION

The present study is focused on risk factors associated with peptic ulcer disease and its management. The disease is more prevalent in males (54%) than in females (46%). The age group 28-37 (30%) is more prone to develop PUD.

Based upon odds ratio, *H. pylori*, NSAIDs, smoking, age, alcohol, tea or coffee intake, tobacco and betel leaves intake have significant strength of association with the occurrence of peptic ulcer disease at significance level of less than 0.05. Other less significant factors were stress and spicy food.

Most common type of peptic ulcer disease observed was gastric ulcer which accounts for 70% of total peptic ulcer disease cases, followed by duodenal ulcer which accounts for 19% and gastroduodenal ulcer 11%.

Triple therapy is most effective treatment for *H.pylori* positive cases which includes use of PPIs, Amoxicillin and Clarithromycin as Pantocid and Nexpro kits. Monotherapy with PPI was instituted in NSAIDs induced Ulcers and *H.pylori* negative cases for 14 days. Widely used PPI is Pantoprazole. Apart from triple and monotherapy it was observed that other combination treatments were given, which includes the use of Ulcer Protective Agents, antacids, H2 receptor blockers (Ranitidine) and prokinetics.

Eradication of *H.pylori* is highly recommended in all perceived patients, NSAIDs used should be closely monitored and stress should be managed. Out of 105 cases, 97(92 %) cases were cured.

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PATIENT INFORMATION AND INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Protocol Title:

RISK FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH PEPTIC ULCER DISEASE AND ITS MANAGEMENT AT A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

Study Conducted by: Ms. Afsha Jabeen, Ms. Hafsa Siddikha, Ms. Madiha Zaheer

Subject No: _____

Dear Participant

You are invited to participate in an observational research study project. Before you agree to take part in this research project you must please read this information sheet as it contains important information to help you decide whether or not it is in your best interest to participate in this project. You are encouraged to ask as many questions as you need in order to be sure that you understand the study procedures, including possible risks and benefits. If you have any questions that are not properly explained or answered in this information leaflet, please feel free to ask someone from the study staff to give you more information.

You had been identified to be included in this study as you have started to intake a drug _____ belong to

The study has been approved by both Scientific Research Committee, Ethics committee of MESCO College of Pharmacy and is in compliance with medical and ethical standards. In addition, the study will be conducted according to the declaration of Helsinki and Good Clinical Practice Guidelines.

Your participation in this study is voluntary. You may choose not to be in the study or leave the study at any time by telling the investigator. If you decide not to be in the study or to withdraw your consent, you will not lose any benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to write objectives .

The study medications had been approved by the FDA, Drug Controller of India and other regulatory authorities.

Approximately sample size participants will be taking part in the study. The expected period of your participation is 6 months.

Study Procedure:

To determine if you are eligible to enter this study you will be asked to do the following: *(brief description of the screening procedures would be given orally)*. If you meet the study inclusion criteria and you agree to participate in the study, you must be willing to co-operate and provide necessary information required for the study and follow the instruction of your doctor and researcher.

During this study while you will be receiving the study drugs the researcher would be observing and recording your write parameters to be collected in Proforma as a result of intake of research drugs.

Do not take any other medication, including **over-the counter, prescription, herbal or traditional**, without first informing the study researcher/doctor.

What are the possible risks and inconveniences of being in the study?

This study is an Observational study that means there would not be any intervention in your prescription drugs that you are already taking advised by your doctor. So there is negligible risk in volunteering this study. Apart from usual side effects/adverse effects of from the study drugs there would be no further health hazard in this study.

What are the possible benefits of being in the study?

The information gained during the study can be useful in obtaining future treatment.

The close medical attention you will get by participating in the study may result in you gaining useful information about your health status.

The researcher will not be liable for any loss, injuries and/or damages which you may sustain **to the extent that** such loss is caused by:

- The use of any other medicine during the study
- Any injury as a result of you not following the prescription instructions, protocol requirements or any instructions or indication which the study doctor/researcher may give to you.
- Any injury arising from any action or lack of action on the part of a third party to deal adequately with a side effect or reaction to the study medication
- An injury arising from negligence on your part

Confidentiality

All records identifying you will be kept confidential and, to the extent permitted by the applicable laws and regulations, will not be made publicly available. The study doctor and research team will use **personal information** about you to conduct this study. This may include your name, address, medical history and information from your study visits. However, this personal information is not included in the **study data** that will be forwarded to any other personal/organization. You will be identified by a numerical number in any reports of publications produced from this study (study data).

To confirm that the study data collected about you is correct and related to you; Studyresearcher, doctor as well as representatives of ethics committees will have access to your personal information at the study site. These persons are required to maintain the confidentiality of your information. By signing this document, you are authorizing such access.

Payment, Expenses and Costs

You will not receive payment for participating in this study, and study related costs such study medication, treatment, tests, examinations and procedures specified in the protocol will be paid for by you. **Neither researcher nor your healthcare provider will be responsible for these expenses.**

Termination of Participation

Your participation in the study may be stopped for the following reasons:

- You don't follow the study researcher/doctor's instructions
- You do not take the study medication as prescribed
- The study researcher/doctor decides that it is in your best interest
- There aren't enough participants in the study of the study has reached the required number of participants

Study Results

You will be able to get information about your study results and the outcome of the study by contacting

Contacts for answers related to the research.

Researcher's 24hr Mobile no.-8106931814, Landline no.....

Consent Statement

By signing below, I agree that:

1. **I have read the information sheet and consent form for this study.**
2. **I have had the chance to answer questions and they were answered to my satisfaction.**
3. **I have been given the time to discuss the information with others and to decide whether or not to take part.**
4. **I will receive a signed and dated copy of this consent form**
5. **I agree to participate in this study**

Name of Subject

Subject Signature

Date

Name of Legally Acceptable Representative

*Signature of Legally Acceptable Representative

Date

Relationship to study participant

Name of Researcher

Signature of Researcher

Date

I hereby verify that verbal consent was obtained from the above participant. The participant has been informed about the risks and the benefits of the research, understands such risks and benefits and is able to give consent to participation, without coercion, undue influence or inappropriate incentives.

Name of Witness

*Signature of Witness

Date

DATA COLLECTION FORM

PATIENT INFORMATION:

IP/OP no:	Date:
Name:	Gender:
Age:	BMI:

OTHER DETAILS:

Family history of PUD:	Food habits:
Lifestyle characteristics:	Exercise:
Sanitation:	occupation

ADDICTIONS :

SMOKING STATUS : non smoker / smoker / former smoker
ALCOHOL : none/occasional(<3 units per week) / light(3-15 units per week) / Moderate(16-24 units per week) / heavy(\geq 25 units per week)
OTHERS :

COMORBID CONDITIONS :

Diabetes	Stress
Hypertension	Depression
CAD	CLD
GERD	Others

CHIEF COMPLAINTS :

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INVESTIGATIONS:

Endoscopic findings:	X-Ray:
Urea breath test:	Double contrast barium radiology:
Stool antigen test:	Biopsy:
Serological test:	Others:

LOCATION OF ULCER:

Gastric ulcer alone:

Duodenal ulcer alone:

Both:

Number of ulcers : Single

Multiple

MEDICATIONS:

PAST(since 1 year):

RECENT(8-30 days):

Current(since 7 days):

FINAL DIAGNOSIS:

Sign of researcher:

sign of supervisor: